

SMARTHEP

REAL-TIME ANALYSIS FOR
SCIENCE AND INDUSTRY

SUMMARY OF NETWORK RESEARCH OUTPUTS

2022 – 2025

SMARTHEP was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, call H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, under Grant Agreement n. 956086

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SMARTHEP: TRAINING PHD STUDENTS IN REAL-TIME ANALYSIS AT THE LHC AND IN INDUSTRY

ESRs: Laura Boggia (IBM/LPNHE Paris), Leon Bozianu (UniGe), Carlos Cocha Toapaxi (Heidelberg U.), Jamie Gooding (TUDO), Joachim Hansen (Lund U.), Pratik Jawahar (Manchester U.), Daniel Magdalinski (NIKHEF/VU), Henrique Pineiro Monteagudo (Verizon/UniBo), Micol Olocco (TU Dortmund)

SMARTHEP: training PhD students in real-time analysis at the LHC and in industry

Johannes Albrecht, Laura Boggia, Leon Bozianu, Andrew Carey, Carlos Cocha, Caterina Doglioni, James Andrew Gooding, Joachim Hansen, Patin Inkaew, Kaare Iversen, Pratik Jawahar, Henning Kirschenmann, Daniel Magdalinski, Alice Ohlson, Micol Olocco, Henrique Piñeiro Monteagudo, Steven Schramm, Mike Sokoloff, Alexandros Sopasakis, Leonardo Taccari, Sten Åstrand
e-Print: 2401.13484 [hep-ex]

DOI: 10.1051/epjconf/202429508022

Published in: EPJ Web Conf. 295 (2024), 08022,

In this invited Editorial for Software and Computing for Big Science, we describe the SMARTHEP Innovative Training Network funded via the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions between 2021 and 2025. SMARTHEP trained 12 PhD students to advance machine learning and real-time analysis in high-energy physics experiments and industrial applications. We present the perspective of students, supervisors, and external observers of the network, concerning the work done within the network, the added value compared to “typical” PhD positions, and the emerging themes and directions from our experiences in the past four years.

THE SMARTHEP EUROPEAN TRAINING NETWORK (CHEP 2023)

ESRs: Jamie Gooding (TUDO), Leon Bozianu (UniGe), Carlos Cocha Toapaxi (Heidelberg U.), Pratik Jawahar (Manchester U.), Micol Olocco (TU Dortmund)

The SMARTHEP European Training Network

James Andrew Gooding Leon Bozianu, Carlos Cocha Toapaxi, Pratik Jawahar, Micol Olocco

e-Print: 2401.13484 [hep-ex]

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Published in: EPJ Web Conf. 295 (2024), 08022,

Synergies between MACHine learning, Real-Time analysis and Hybrid architectures for efficient Event Processing and decision-making (SMARTHEP) is a European Training Network, training a new generation of Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) to advance real-time decision-making, driving data-collection and analysis towards synonymy. SMARTHEP brings together scientists from major LHC collaborations at the frontiers of real-time analysis (RTA) and key specialists from computer science and industry. By solving concrete problems as a community, SMARTHEP will further the adoption of RTA techniques, enabling future High Energy Physics (HEP) discoveries and generating impact in industry. ESRs will contribute to European growth, leveraging their hands-on experience in machine learning and accelerators towards commercial deliverables in fields that can profit most from RTA, e.g., transport, manufacturing, and finance. This contribution presents the training and outreach plan for the network, and is intended as an opportunity for further collaboration and feedback from the CHEP community.

SMARTEP

REAL-TIME ANALYSIS FOR
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WORK PACKAGE 3:

Machine learning and advanced data analysis

SMARTEP was funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, call H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020, under Grant Agreement n. 956086

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REVIEW OF MACHINE LEARNING FOR REAL-TIME ANALYSIS AT THE LARGE HADRON COLLIDER EXPERIMENTS ALICE, ATLAS, CMS AND LHCb

ESR Lead Editor: Leon Bozianu,
and authorlist below

Review of Machine Learning for Real-Time Analysis at the Large Hadron Collider experiments ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb

Laura Boggia, Carlos Cocha, Fotis Giasemis, Joachim Hansen, Patin Inkaew, Kaare Endrup Iversen, Pratik Jawahar, Henrique Pineiro Monteagudo, Micol Olocco, Sten Astrand, Martino Borsato, Leon Bozianu, Steven Schramm, the SMARTHEP Network

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2506.14578

e-Print: 2506.14578 [physics.hep-ex]

The field of high energy physics (HEP) has seen a marked increase in the use of machine learning (ML) techniques in recent years. The proliferation of applications has revolutionised many aspects of the data processing pipeline at collider experiments including the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). In this whitepaper, we discuss the increasingly crucial role that ML plays in real-time analysis (RTA) at the LHC, namely in the context of the unique challenges posed by the trigger systems of the large LHC experiments. We describe a small selection of the ML applications in use at the large LHC experiments to demonstrate the breadth of use-cases. We continue by emphasising the importance of collaboration and engagement between the HEP community and industry, highlighting commonalities and synergies between the two. The mutual benefits are showcased in several interdisciplinary examples of RTA from industrial contexts. This whitepaper, compiled by the SMARTHEP network, offers a high-level overview of specific real-time use cases.

BALER -- MACHINE LEARNING BASED COMPRESSION OF SCIENTIFIC DATA

ESR: Pratik Jawahar (University of Manchester)

Baler -- Machine Learning Based Compression of Scientific Data

Fritjof Bengtsson, Caterina Doglioni, Per Alexander Ekman, Axel Gallén, Pratik Jawahar et al.

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2305.02283

e-Print: 2305.02283 [physics.comp-ph]

In this paper, we document the development and applications of Baler – a Machine Learning based data compression tool for use across scientific disciplines and industry. Here, we present Baler's performance for the compression of High Energy Physics (HEP) data, as well as its application to Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) toy data as a proof-of-principle. We also present suggestions for cross-disciplinary guidelines to enable feasibility studies for machine learning based compression for scientific data. *Pratik's contribution* involved being one of the three main ML algorithm developers, with specific expertise in PyTorch.

A ZERO-KNOWLEDGE MACHINE LEARNING AND CRYPTOGRAPHIC HASHING-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFIABLE, LOW LATENCY INFERENCE AT THE LHC

ESR: Pratik Jawahar (University of Manchester)
Secondment host: CERN

Knowledge is Overrated: A zero-knowledge machine learning and cryptographic hashing-based framework for verifiable, low latency inference at the LHC

Pratik Jawahar, Caterina Doglioni, Maurizio Pierini

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2511.12592

e-Print: 2511.12592 [physics.hep-ex]

PHAZE is a Python and Rust based package that uses cryptographic techniques, like probabilistic hashing and zero knowledge proofs, as the building blocks for a verifiable, ultra-low latency ML inference framework. Current strategies for deploying ML models in low level triggers are heavily latency and memory constrained. PHAZE is a novel re-imagination of future trigger algorithms that overcomes this issue using less explored areas of research like early-exit ML models and cryptographic primitives. We have shown its capabilities in simple proof-of-principle examples, and we intend to pursue further research along this line to make PHAZE-like triggers a possibility in the future. *Pratik* was the sole developer of the project.

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WORK PACKAGE 4:

Hybrid compute architectures

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GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK-BASED PIPELINE FOR TRACK FINDING IN THE VELO AT LHCb

ESR: Fotis Giasemis (LPNHE and LIP6)

Graph Neural Network-Based Pipeline for Track Finding in the Velo at LHCb

Anthony Correia, Fotis I. Giasemis, Nabil Garroum, Vladimir Vava, Gligorov, Bertrand Granado

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2406.12869

e-Print: 2406.12869 [physics.ins-det]

The next decade will see an order of magnitude increase in data collected by high-energy physics experiments, driven by the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC). The reconstruction of charged particle trajectories (tracks) has always been a critical part of offline data processing pipelines. The complexity of HL-LHC data will however increasingly mandate track finding in all stages of an experiment's real-time processing. This paper presents a GNN-based track-finding pipeline tailored for the Run 3 LHCb experiment's vertex detector and benchmarks its physics performance and computational cost against existing classical algorithms on GPU architectures. A novelty of our work compared to existing GNN tracking pipelines is batched execution, in which the GPU evaluates the pipeline on hundreds of events in parallel. We evaluate the impact of neural-network quantisation on physics and computational performance, and comment on the outlook for GNN tracking algorithms for other parts of the LHCb track-finding pipeline.

GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK-BASED TRACK FINDING IN THE LHCb VERTEX DETECTOR

ESR: Fotis Giasemis (LPNHE and LIP6)

Graph Neural Network-based track finding in the LHCb vertex detector

Anthony Correia, Fotis I. Giasemis, Nabil Garroum, Vladimir Vava Gligorov, Bertrand Granado

e-Print: 2407.12119 [physics.ins-det]

DOI: 10.1088/1748-0221/19/12/P12022

Published in: JINST 19 (2024) 12, P12022

As particle colliders increase their number of simultaneous collisions, and detectors become more granular to face this increase, the generated data overwhelms our standard data-taking and computing methods. The traditional algorithms used to reconstruct particle paths (tracks) become slower as the data volume grows, presenting a bottleneck for real-time analysis. This project proposes a shift to Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), a type of AI that handles complex data connections more efficient, and tailor it specifically for the LHCb experiment. LHCb relies on Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) for its real-time decision making system. The proposed model, ETX4VELO, implemented on CPUs and GPUs, proved it could identify particle tracks with higher purity than current methods, significantly cutting down on "fake" tracks and better spotting electrons. The focus of future work is then to ensure that this prototype can be deployed at scale on the experiment's GPU farm.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FPGA AND GPU PERFORMANCE FOR MACHINE LEARNING-BASED TRACK RECONSTRUCTION AT LHCb

ESR: Fotis Giasemis (LPNHE and LIP6)

Comparative Analysis of FPGA and GPU Performance for Machine Learning-Based Track Reconstruction at LHCb

Fotis I. Giasemis, Vladimir Loncar, Bertrand Granado, Vladimir Vava Gligorov

e-Print: 2502.02304 [hep-ex]

DOI: 10.1109/NewCAS64648.2025.11106977

Contribution to the NewCAS Conference 2025

In high-energy physics, the increasing luminosity and detector granularity at the Large Hadron Collider are driving the need for more efficient data processing solutions. Machine Learning has emerged as a promising tool for reconstructing charged particle tracks, due to its potentially linear computational scaling with detector hits. The recent implementation of a graph neural network-based track reconstruction pipeline in the first level trigger of the LHCb experiment on GPUs serves as a platform for comparative studies between computational architectures in the context of high-energy physics. This paper presents a novel comparison of the throughput of ML model inference between FPGAs and GPUs, focusing on the first step of the track reconstruction pipeline—an implementation of a multilayer perceptron. Using HLS4ML for FPGA deployment, we benchmark its performance against the GPU implementation and demonstrate the potential of FPGAs for high-throughput, low-latency inference without the need for an expertise in FPGA development and while consuming significantly less power

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WORK PACKAGE 5:

Decision-making in research and industry

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SUMMARY OF THE TRIGGER SYSTEMS OF THE LARGE HADRON COLLIDER EXPERIMENTS ALICE, ATLAS, CMS AND LHCb

ESR Lead Editor: Jamie Gooding,
and authorlist below

Review of Machine Learning for Real-Time Analysis at the Large Hadron Collider experiments ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb

*Johannes Albrecht, Leon Bozianu, Lukas Calefice,
Sofia Cella, Carlos Eduardo Cocha Toapaxi, Caterina
Doglioni, Kaare Endrup Iversen, Vladimir Gligorov,
James Andrew Gooding, Patin Inkaew, Daniel
Magdalinski, Alexandros Sopasakis, Danielle Joan
Wilson-Edwards, The SMARTHEP network*

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2506.14578

e-Print: 2408.03881 [physics.hep-ex]

In modern High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments, triggers perform the important task of selecting, in real time, the data to be recorded and saved for physics analyses. As a result, trigger strategies play a key role in extracting relevant information from the vast streams of data produced at facilities like the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). As the energy and luminosity of the collisions increase, these strategies must be upgraded and maintained to suit the experimental needs. This whitepaper compiled by the SMARTHEP Early Stage Researchers presents a high-level overview and reviews recent developments of triggering practices employed at the LHC. The general trigger principles applied at modern HEP experiments are highlighted, with specific reference to the current trigger state-of-the-art within the ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb collaborations. Furthermore, a brief synopsis of the new trigger paradigm required by the upcoming high-luminosity upgrade of the LHC is provided.

THE ATLAS TRIGGER SYSTEM FOR LHC RUN 3 AND TRIGGER PERFORMANCE IN 2022

ESR: Sofia Cella (CERN)

The ATLAS trigger system for LHC Run 3 and trigger performance in 2022.

ATLAS Collaboration,
e-Print: 2401.06630 [hep-ex]

DOI: 10.1088/1748-0221/19/06/P06029

Published in: JINST 19 (2024) 06, P06029

Abstract: The ATLAS trigger system is a crucial component of the ATLAS experiment at the LHC. It is responsible for selecting events in line with the ATLAS physics programme. This paper presents an overview of the changes to the trigger and data acquisition system during the second long shutdown of the LHC, and shows the performance of the trigger system and its components in the proton-proton collisions during the 2022 commissioning period as well as its expected performance in the third LHC data-taking period (2022–2025). *Sofia contributed* studies on the HLT software performance scaling as a function of the number of events processed in parallel using different parallelisation approaches.

THE ATLAS RUN-3 TRIGGER MENU

ESR: Sofia Cella (CERN)

The ATLAS Run-3 Trigger Menu

Sofia Cella (CERN)

DOI: 10.22323/1.476.0943

Published in: PoS ICHEP2024 (2025), 943

Abstract. The ATLAS experiment in the LHC Run 3 is recording up to 3 kHz of fully-built physics collision events out of an LHC bunch crossing rate of up to 40 MHz, with additional rate dedicated to partial readout. A two-level trigger system selects events of interest to cover a wide variety of physics while rejecting a high rate of background events. The selection of events targets both generic physics signatures, such as high- p_T leptons, jets, missing energy, as well as more specific physics signatures, such as long-lived particles or di-Higgs events.

An overview of the ATLAS trigger menu system is presented, highlighting the new developments and changes for Run 3.

Sofia contributed studies on the HLT software performance scaling as a function of the number of events processed in parallel using different parallelisation approaches.

TRIGGERCALIB: A TURNKEY PACKAGE FOR ESTIMATING LHCb TRIGGER EFFICIENCIES

ESR: Jamie Gooding

TriggerCalib: a turnkey package for estimating LHCb trigger efficiencies

Johannes Albrecht, James Andrew Gooding, Maxim Lysenko, Abhijit Mathad, Alessandro Scarabotto

DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2505.15951

e-Print: 2505.15951 [hep-ex]

Estimations of trigger efficiencies are essential to LHCb physics analyses. A data-driven method, dubbed TISTOS, provides a framework in which to estimate such efficiencies by identifying whether candidates were selected because of the presence of a signal signature (TOS), because of another signature in the event (TIS), or both. I revalidated this method and developed a software package, TriggerCalib, to provide a centralised implementation of these calculations. In this paper, of which I am corresponding author, the formalism and implementation are presented, demonstrated for $B^+ \rightarrow J/\psi K^+$ decay candidates in simulated LHCb data, along with a discussion of statistical and systematic uncertainty estimation.

SOFTWARE FOR MANUFACTURING WITH P8

ESR: Daniel Magdalinski (NIKHEF/VU)
Secondment host: Point-8 GmbH

Software for manufacturing with P8 (1.0).

Author(s): Magdalinski, D.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15024311

Publisher: Zenodo (2025)

This project was completed by Daniel Magdalinski during a 2.5-month secondment at Point 8 GmbH in Dortmund and focuses on detecting peaks in industrial time-series data. A 1D Unet-based CNN model was developed for segmentation of the active regions of the time-series. The project is detailed in a repository which provides the code used for preprocessing data and training of the model as well as showcasing the results on synthetic data.

LEARNING TRAFFIC ANOMALIES FROM GENERATIVE MODELS ON REAL-TIME OBSERVATIONS

ESR: Fotis Giasemis (LPNHE and LIP6)
Secondment host: Ximantis

*Learning Traffic Anomalies from Generative Models on
Real-Time Observations*

Fotis I. Giasemis, Alexandros Sopasakis

[DOI:10.48550/arXiv.2502.01391](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.01391)

e-Print: 2502.01391 [cs.LG]

Accurate detection of traffic anomalies is crucial for effective urban traffic management and congestion mitigation. We use the Spatiotemporal Generative Adversarial Network (STGAN) framework combining Graph Neural Networks and Long Short-Term Memory networks to capture complex spatial and temporal dependencies in traffic data. We apply STGAN to real-time, minute-by-minute observations from 42 traffic cameras across Gothenburg, Sweden, collected over several months in 2020. The images are processed to compute a flow metric representing vehicle density, which serves as input for the model. Training is conducted on data from April to November 2020, and validation is performed on a separate dataset from November 14 to 23, 2020. Our results demonstrate that the model effectively detects traffic anomalies with high precision and low false positive rates. The detected anomalies include camera signal interruptions, visual artifacts, and extreme weather conditions affecting traffic flow.

TRAFFIC PREDICTIONS USING GRAPH NEURAL NETWORKS ON REAL-TIME OBSERVATIONS

ESR: Joachim Hansen (Lund University)
Secondment host: Ximantis

Traffic predictions using graph neural networks.

Joachim Hansen, Donglin Liu and Alexandros Sopasakis

DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.14725.46566

Published in: 'Advances in Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence', Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Advances in Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence (ASPAI' 2025), 8-10 April 2025, Innsbruck, Austria, Ed. by Sergey Y. Yurish

This work demonstrates the robustness of the application of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to real-time traffic density prediction, using computer vision data from the Swedish Transport Administration (Trafikverket). A variable temporal embedding architecture was introduced to capture dynamic traffic behavior over time, enhancing the predictive performance of the model. *Joachim was one of three editors and a principal contributor to the analysis, responsible for improving the algorithm, data preparation, developing the deep learning pipeline for density estimation, preprocessing the observational data, and training the GNN models in close collaboration with co-authors.*

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WORK PACKAGE 6:

Monitoring and discoveries

SMARTHEP was funded by the
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AN OBJECT DETECTION APPROACH FOR LANE CHANGE AND OVERTAKE DETECTION FROM MOTION PROFILES

ESR: Henrique Pineiro Monteagudo
(Verizon Connect)

***An Object Detection Approach for Lane Change
and Overtake Detection from Motion Profiles***

*A. Benericetti, N. Bellaccini, H. P. Monteagudo, M.
Simoncini and F. Sambo*

[DOI:10.1109/ITSC57777.2023.10422014](https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC57777.2023.10422014)

*2023 IEEE 26th International Conference on
Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), Bilbao,
Spain, 2023, pp. 1389-1394,*

This conference paper presents the idea of using an object detector to identify vehicle maneuvers in a compressed representation of a video known as motion profile (an image obtained by averaging the pixel values of a strip of pixel around the horizon). *Henrique contributed in performing part of the experiments and writing sections of the manuscript.*

RENDBEV: SEMANTIC NOVEL VIEW SYNTHESIS FOR SELF-SUPERVISED BIRD'S EYE VIEW SEGMENTATION

ESR: Henrique Pineiro Monteagudo
(Verizon Connect)

RendBEV: Semantic Novel View Synthesis for Self-Supervised Bird's Eye View Segmentation

H. P. Monteagudo, L. Taccari, A. Pjetri, F. Sambo and S. Salti

DOI:10.1109/WACV61041.2025.00062.

2025 IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision (WACV), Tucson, AZ, USA, 2025, pp. 535-544

This paper introduces RendBEV, a novel method to train bird's eye view semantic segmentation networks (a representation of the environment commonly used in assisted and automated driving applications) in a self-supervised manner. The method uses differentiable volumetric rendering together with pretrained semantic segmentation networks and neural density fields. It is the first method able to train these networks without using any bird's eye view ground truth labels.

Henrique contributed the original idea, developed the software, carried out the experiments, and wrote most of the article's text.

VIEWPOINTDEPTH: A NEW DATASET FOR MONOCULAR DEPTH ESTIMATION UNDER VIEWPOINT SHIFTS

ESR: Henrique Pineiro Monteagudo
(Verizon Connect)

*ViewpointDepth: A New Dataset for Monocular
Depth Estimation Under Viewpoint Shifts,*

A. Pjetri et al.,

DOI:10.1109/IV64158.2025.11097590.

*2025 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV),
Cluj-Napoca, Romania, 2025, pp. 406-411,*

This paper introduces a dataset captured by dashcams with the goal of studying how changes in viewpoint (camera mounting position and orientation) affect the performance of machine learning models. *Henrique contributed* with part of the data collection design and monitoring, data processing, as well as manuscript editing and revision.

SMARTHEP SECONDMENT SOFTWARE: ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL DATA WITH LIGHTBOX

ESRs: Sofia Cella (CERN), Leon Bozianu (UniGe)
Secondment host: Lightbox

***SMARTHEP secondment software: analysis of
financial data with Lightbox***

Author(s): Bozianu, Leon; Cella, Sofia

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14566354

Publisher: Zenodo

This open-source codebase outlines the work of ESR 3 and ESR 4 in the secondment work at Lightbox, a financial services firm based in London and Geneva. The project applied novel machine learning techniques to time series data from financial markets. We tested and evaluated several deep learning frameworks for real time analysis and predictive forecasting using cutting-edge technical indicators. The released open-source code was solely developed by the ESRs using publicly available financial data.

BANKING ACTIVITY SIMULATOR SOFTWARE

ESR: Micol Olocco (TU Dortmund)
Secondment host: IBM

Banking Activity Simulator Software

Micol Olocco, Pierre Feillet,

GitHub link:

<https://github.com/GeNovae/banking-activity-simulator>

Developed during the ESR8's industry secondment at IBM France Lab Saclay, this work presents a flexible and open-source framework for simulation realistic banking transaction data, designed to address the dual challenges of data scarcity and privacy compliance in financial fraud research. Initially based on static probabilistic models, the framework has evolved into a Large Language Model (LLM)-driven architecture. The resulting synthetic datasets could offer a configurable environment for developing and testing fraud detection strategies—without the constraints of proprietary banking data.

SYNTHETIC DATA GENERATION WITH LORENZETTI FOR TIME SERIES ANOMALY DETECTION IN HIGH-ENERGY PHYSICS CALORIMETERS

ESR: Laura Boggia (IBM/LPNHE Paris)

***Synthetic Data Generation with Lorenzetti for Time Series
Anomaly Detection in High-Energy Physics Calorimeters***
Laura Boggia, Bogdan Malaescu
e-Print: 2509.07451 [hep-ex]

Submitted as Proceedings of the EuCAIF Conference 2025

Reliable data quality monitoring is essential for modern high-energy physics experiments, where vast streams of detector signals must be continuously validated. In this work, we explore advanced machine learning methods for anomaly detection in multivariate time series, aiming to automatically identify unusual detector behavior. Working in collaboration with the team behind the Lorenzetti Simulator, I implemented and evaluated methods using synthetic calorimeter data with injected anomalies.

BENCHMARKING UNSUPERVISED STRATEGIES FOR ANOMALY DETECTION IN MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES

ESR: Laura Boggia (IBM/LPNHE Paris)

***Benchmarking Unsupervised Strategies for Anomaly
Detection in Multivariate Time Series***

Laura Boggia, Rafael Teixeira de Lima, Bogdan Malaescu

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.07451>

e-Print: 2506.20574 [cs-LG]

This work explores transformer-based methods for anomaly detection in multivariate time series, focusing on the recently proposed iTransformer architecture. *Laura led the study*, including the main implementations, computational experiments, and paper writing. Although not specific to high-energy physics, the results provide valuable insights for data quality monitoring and automated fault detection in complex experimental systems.

ENRICHING THE PHYSICS PROGRAM OF THE CMS EXPERIMENT VIA DATA SCOUTING AND DATA PARKING

ESR: Patin Inkaew (Helsinki)

Enriching the physics program of the CMS experiment via data scouting and data parking

CMS Collaboration, e-Print: 2403.16134 [hep-ex]

DOI:10.1016/j.physrep.2024.09.006

Published in: Phys.Rept. 1115 (2025), 678-772

This paper is the first CMS collaboration's review on data scouting and data parking programs, alternative trigger strategies, overcoming bandwidth limitations and enabling higher data-taking rate. These strategies help unlock physics regions inaccessible with conventional strategy. It describes collective developments from their origins in the first data-taking period Run 1 of LHC (2011-2012), their evolution in Run 2 (2015-2018), early results and future prospects for commencing Run 3 (2022-2026), and analyses utilising scouting or parking data. As a part of Run 3 development, *Patin Inkaew investigated* potential advantages with jet scouting triggers in gluon-gluon fusion produced Higgs boson decaying to bottom quark-antiquark pairs, a yet directly discovered process predicted by the Standard Model. The result shows promising increases, particularly in the regime of Higgs boson with low transverse momentum where traditional triggers are inefficient.

BEAD: BACKGROUND ENRICHMENT FOR ANOMALY DETECTION FRAMEWORK

ESR: Pratik Jawahar (University of Manchester)

PRAkTIKaI24/BEAD: Background Enrichment for Anomaly Detection [Framework] (v0.17.4).

Pratik Jawahar, Ioannis (Yannis) Kalaitzidis, & Abhishek Kotwani. (2025).

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17117302

Publisher: Zenodo (2025).

BEAD is a Python package that uses deep learning based methods for anomaly detection in HEP data for new physics searches. BEAD has been designed with modularity in mind, to enable usage of various unsupervised latent variable models for anomaly detection by design, but any tasks beyond this scope as well with easily customizable modules. *Pratik* is the primary developer and maintainer of this software package.